

Navigating Insights and Perspectives of Students with Disability to Include in Nepalese Classroom

Khagendra Baraily

Department of Special Education Sanothimi Campus, Tribhuvan University

Corresponding Author: Khagendra Baraily khagendraji@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Untrained Teacher, Expanded Core Curriculum, Domination of Traditional Method, Psychological Attachment

Received : 10, November

Revised : 20, December

Accepted: 25, January

©2024 Baraily: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Integrated schools with resource classes and special schools provide education for children with disability in Nepal. Government funds and the partial support of national and internal donor partners run these schools. This study intends to seek how children with disability normalize in regular classes after the additional support service in resource class to become a case of inclusion in the education system of Nepal. The study explored the adjustment challenges and identified coping strategies in a regular course. The four students with disability from integrated schools representing children with visual impairment and children with deaf were purposively selected and interviewed through semi-structured interview guidelines in a natural setting. The interview responses were transcribed verbatim and analyzed by extracting themes within a theoretical framework based on post-structuralism and discourse analysis. The study explored significant challenges such as the lack of disabled-friendly physical facilities, domination of traditional methods, presence of an untrained teacher, lack of expanded core curriculum, lack of peer support and poor psychological attachment. The exploration of challenges assists policymakers and well educators set up strategies for effective inclusion in school education and the community.

INTRODUCTION

In my teaching carrier, I spent nearly ten years teaching students in public and institutionalized schools. Tracking to the remarkable event in my life, I got an opportunity to instruct in an integrated school. Mainly I taught in a general class containing visually impaired students. When I commenced my instruction related to arithmetic, the students with visual impairment entertained equally with their non-disabled peers. The extraordinary situation was that when I held the class about mathematics under the topic of algebra and geometry, the children with visual impairment started murmuring, roaming to the resource room to learn music and other engaged activity like computers and so forth. They could not understand an algebraic symbol in Braille script. I did not know Braille to present the algebraic expression.

Consequently, they could not write algebraic symbols and geometric figures on their slate with a stylus. In such circumstances, I realized I was not supporting them to accommodate them in the regular classroom. I saw that the children with visual impairment face the challenges of adjustment in a regular class with non-disabled peers. The situation of question is about how children with visual impairment are mainstreamed in the traditional classroom and how I could educate them with the delivery of additional support encountering my cognition. This matter of thought always pinched my heart. It inspired me to study the situation to explore significant challenges faced by children with visual impairment in the regular classroom so that they could easily adjust to a mainstream environment.

Most of the research findings have shown that the attitude of teachers and principals is negative and resistant to placing children with visual impairment in regular due to the varieties of restrictions (Neeraja & Anuradha, 2014). Generally, the principal denies the obligation on the side of disability by raising several issues. From the behavior of teachers and principals, it is thought that there is discrimination in either exclusion or difficulty for a student enrolled (Wang, 2016). The definition of inclusion in policy is only limited to integration and is always ambiguous about fulfilling inclusive indicators (Soodak & McCarthy, 2013). There is always a debatable issue in the discourse of inclusion (Liasidou, 2012). The policy practice implementation is running far behind the epicenter of inclusion. The stakeholders are roaming surface-wise with the skip of policy implementation (Barnes & Mercer, 2005). The bundles of complaints are commonly directed against administrators (Sucuoglu et al., 2010). Many teachers and head teachers still deny they have any obligation to accept students with disability (Cox & Dykes, 2001).

It is hoped that if students with disability are in the regular class, they are likely to perform better (Forlin, 1995). In the practice of including, students with disabilities can go to general class without an aide. They can do the assignment, develop math skills, and have written language components (Hemann, 2007). The mutual social setting creates collaboration within the class (Neeraja & Anuradha, 2014). An accommodation that students with disability need are provided in the regular classroom, but the students with disability may not feel the beautiful situations in the school (Mitchell et al., 2015). If the challenge frequently occurs in the school, the students with a disability won't be

motivated to perform at the pace of the rest and fit in as much as possible (DiGennaro Reed et al., 2011).

Sometimes, without the necessary support, entire curricular content and fast pace expectation in the regular class, students with disability may experience frustration (Leach & Duffy, 2009). This frustration may cause feelings of inferiority and possibly behavior concern, causing students to shut down and not try (Bos et al., 2002). A student with a disability generally benefits from the regular classroom when they become part of everyday activities (Vaughn et al., 2002)

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review is a piece of academic writing accompanying academic literature concerning choosing a topic in its analytical context. The works related to changes students and teachers face in regular classes are taught in this portion. The coping strategies for mainstreaming are also studied and incorporated in this context.

Barriers faced by Students with Special Needs

The gain of mainstreaming is inclusion, that's worldwide demand of present society, and it has disadvantages. Students with disability intend to disrupt the classroom with emotional and behavioral issues (Pugach, 2005). Most people suppose that they're cognitively below compared to sighted friends. The knowledge-gaining procedure isn't robust as anticipated (Yan et al., 2019). Usually, it seems challenging to meet the needs of students with disability for every teacher. Teacher needs to treat differently for youngsters with special needs (Kurth & Keegan, 2014). The kids with unique wishes are deprived of appropriate schooling when they may be taught utilizing mismatching with regular class students. In the science education class, youngsters with visual impairment are disadvantaged because of their visual disability and the curriculum isn't geared to encompass them (Wilhelmsen & Sørensen, 2017). This propels school students with the incapacity to struggle against discrimination and bullying from their counterparts. It could motivate students with visual impairment to feel frustration, low self-esteem, isolation, melancholy and aggression (Lohmeier, 2005).

The notion of self and environment for youngsters with visual disabilities is based on imagination but now not facts (Maltz, 1962). The person accomplishes what he insights in himself or his surroundings. Children with low vision are stricken by their self-concept and struggle to identify as sighted or blind. Baraga & Van Kampen (1983) expresses that the one-of-a-kind improvement elements are hindered by detachment from the physical environment.

Children with visual impairment can note the opportunity to gain insights through visual input as they've less chance to explore their surrounding understanding. The substantial experience can secure Mobility consists of components such as mental orientation and bodily locomotion. Chomba et al. (2014) assert that intellectual direction recognizes the

environment units' spatial relation to itself. Locomotion is movement from one region to any other through the organic mechanism. These aren't separate but limited. If the blind pupil can concentrate on a few sounds about their destination, he must comply with the safe path without any obstacles. Blind students need to use realistic senses (Agesa, 2014).

Dekker (1993) asserts that the acquisition of behavioral patterns by imitation is limited for blind individuals. The child's development concerning posture, learning to walk, talking, playing, expressive movement and other actions are severely affected by those factors. The visual deficit hinders daily activities such as eating, being adequately dressed, transportation facilities, and shopping in the store.

Compensatory Skills

Compensatory skills are required to get admission to the middle curriculum for kids with visible disabilities. With the mastery of this skill, the blind scholar can compete with sighted peers in gaining knowledge of (Dekker, 1993). Compensatory talents correspond with education and offer idea development, spatial know-how, organizational abilities and version required for accessing all regions of the current curriculum (Hatlen, 1996). Students with a visual impairment might also use Braille, considerable print material, ordinary print, tactile symbols, calendars and machines, and recorded speaking devices. The subsequent is the primary issue to be addressed for kids with visual impairment.

Orientation and Mobility Skill

Mobility means the capability to move around independently utilizing a protective manner. Orientation and mobility abilities are components of the expanded core curriculum and an important studying region (Sapp & Hatlen, 2010). The trainer desires to gain knowledge explicitly about mobility skills to train blind students. The cutting-edge curriculum isn't always embracing education provision. The teacher chooses to recognition on educating such capabilities to move freely by using amusing learning with the surroundings (Lohmeier, 2005).

Recreation and leisure skill

Recreation and entertainment talents are crucial for every individual with special needs besides the core ability. An extracurricular activity develops teaming, grouping abilities, and bodily fitness (Sapp & Hatlen, 2010). These abilities are suitable for visually impaired college students, and they need to broaden sports associated with them to enjoy grownup lifestyles (Moser, 2000). The sighted scholar can pick out suitable recreational movement by inspection. However, the visually impaired can't. Therefore, they have to be planned and correctly taught lifelong abilities (Schumm & Vaughn, 1991)

METHODOLOGY

This study was based on phenomenology as a research design, an essential wing of qualitative research. This design digs out the meaning of the

lived experiences of students in social settings and the shared meaning of similar experiences (Creswell, 2013). In the undergoing study, the adopted design helps to study the students' lived experience in regular class (Neubauer et al., 2019). The experience and narratives are drawn from the social setting of the general course based on values and beliefs (Van Lankveld et al., 2017). The students who participated in this study were struggling in regular school. The students who took the traditional class had transformed from the resource class. The participant students only learn Braille and music in the resource class and attend regular classes for mainstream education. Furthermore, they participated in extracurricular activities such as quiz contests, debates and singing competitions organized by the school. Purposively four students with disability from the secondary level were selected as a participant from the integrated school in Kathmandu Valley.

Regarding ethical issues, the participants were informed consent by meeting in a resource class. Confidentiality had been maintained by using pseudo names. In-depth interviews via semi-structured question had taken to gather vital information. The students who participated in this study had experienced different instruction in resource and regular classes. Data analysis revealed the themes of collaboration and interactions with students. Interviews with the participants were recorded by audio recorder. Recorded interview responses were transcribed verbatim and developed code. Similar codes were organized to generate a theme. Likewise, themes were classified as the central theme of the study. Themes were illustrated based on ground data and compared and contrasted with data to data and literature.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result obtained from the information provided by the profound interview with the participant associates with the result of the study. This result is intercourse with post-structuralism and discourse analysis. The significant themes leading to this study's conclusion are discussed below.

Lack of Disable Friendly Physical Facilities

The tangible facility provided by the school for children with disability embraces the mitigating factor for the barrier to education (BICHI & IMAM, 2020). If the infrastructure is disabled-friendly, it is considered to fulfil one aspect of inclusion (Ivancevich & Gilbert, 2000). In this context, one of the participants, S1, said, I cannot see entirely, and it always feels challenging to go to school. There is no disable friendly environment in school, and sometimes, I have fallen down the drain and have felt difficulty sitting in the classroom. Sometimes furniture may break, and I dropped due to a lack of knowledge about the situation furniture.

In this assertion, the existing physical infrastructure is not disabled-friendly and faces many transportation-related problems. Due to the lack of visual impairment-friendly roads, pathways, and classrooms, the children may fall into an accident (Kumar et al., n.d.). The furniture is not also visually impairment friendly. As a result, the student may lose by damage. In such a

scenario, inclusion cannot be ensured without providing suitable physical infrastructure (Vakil et al., 2009). Inclusive schools need to begin setting up disable friendly environments within the school. The school needs to build every aspect of the school, such as furniture, classroom and other facilities, according to the nature of the disability. Another participant S2 said, I go to school by wheelchair. There is no suitable place to move everywhere in the school. So I have not seen a different section in my school. I have to sit near the door because there is no good place to move around. I cannot participate in every activity in the classroom due to my physical condition. My non-disabled peers actively participate in classroom activities, but I cannot.

In the above statement, the academic environment created by the school is not disabling-friendly. The classroom management is not supporting the students with physical disabilities along with low vision (Zaunda et al., 2018). Due to the insufficient place to move the wheelchair, he has to sit near the door. This situation is a toolkit for the learner. In such cases, the student cannot interact with friends by his seating condition. The school management needs to think about a comprehensive classroom so that students with physical disabilities can roam everywhere during instruction for suitable interaction (Preeti & Kiran, 2012). Another participant S3 said, My eye has a shared vision problem, and I cannot see the writing on the whiteboard. The setting of the board is more traditional, and I need to listen to the teacher's sounds but not his demonstration. I could get support from resource class from a resource teacher. The classroom management is not supporting me.

From this assertion, it is clear that the respective participant is of low vision and cannot see the teacher's demonstration. So teachers must manage large printed materials and assistive devices for students with low ideas (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2012). If the students cannot see the board correctly, the teacher must address the intelligent board in large font.

Domination of Traditional Teaching Method

The principle of instructional method guides our existing teaching pedagogy, which is under the domination of traditional thought in teaching. The lecture method is frequently used in the present teaching approach (Ruhl & Suritsky, 1995). This method is adopted regardless of the diversity management strategy. In this context, student S1 said, I cannot understand the content of science and mathematics. The regular teacher demonstrates the teaching module on the whiteboard, but I cannot see it. Until now, I have not experienced the teaching of a regular teacher in Braille script. I try to write in Braille on my stylus but fill in confusion. In mathematics, I cannot understand geometry and algebra because there is no symbolic mechanism in Braille script.

In the above version of the participant, the teacher's instruction is still guided by the conventional method and lacks to introduce modern methods in teaching. Most regular teachers do not have Braille knowledge, so their education is dominated by the lecture method (Kendall, 2018). The students with visual impairment write and note down the teacher's instruction on the slate with Braille script, but the teacher cannot correct it if something is missing

in the student's write-up. So schools need to manage teachers who know Braille (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2012). Otherwise, the knowledge level of students with visual impairment cannot be improved. With the teacher's direct instruction, the students with visual impairment have still been marginalized. In this context, another student S2 asserted, In the regular classroom, most of the teaching methods fall under the traditional instructional approaches. The teachers taught higher content, but I could not understand what he taught. The regular teacher teaches computers as theoretical subjects for us. There is no disabled-friendly computer for practicals in school.

In the above assertion, the existing pedagogy adopted by the teacher in a regular class is wholly oriented to the direct instruction method, and ways of presenting the content are based upon the teacher-centered process (Wilson & Sindelar, 1991). The teacher's presentation dominates the student's activities. In such cases, students' activeness and engagement fall under the miracle of shadow. The teacher needs to adopt a student engagement method for effective adjustment in a regular class (Al-Makahleh, 2011). Children with visual impairment must be educated in tactile and Braille manners. In the above context, student S3 said as, In the unit test, I am excluded because there is only a provision for the writer in the final examination. In such cases, I cannot get the opportunity to improve my reading, along with frequent feedback from the respective teacher.

In this quotation, students are excluded from the opportunity of improving their potential because they read with hard effort in the classroom. Still, they are unable to give their qualifying test in Braille because the national examination board of Nepal has not managed test papers in Braille even though the explicit provision is included in the constitution of Nepal. Due to the lack of policy implementation, students with visual impairment are still back warded to grab such opportunities (Hong et al., 2017). If the willingness comes from the government sector, the provision of test administration in Braille is a difficult task; the attention of the national examination board should come to that side because there is no necessary human resource in the market (Bickford & Falco, 2012).

Presence of an Untrained Teacher

The presence of unskilled teachers for teaching inclusive education in the regular class precludes the opportunity for active participation. The teacher prepares and attends the course through the lens of traditional students and is unaware of differently able children (Wall, 2002). In this context, participant S3 said, I read in class nine and always faced the problem of listening. I see everything on the board. Whatever the teacher demonstrates see only the figure and diagram, but I cannot understand what the picture is illustrating teacher could present the subject matter. I would be able to grasp content and its illustration.

In the present school scenario, the teacher recruited in the regular school is untrained and beyond the skill of inclusive teaching. The teacher is guided by the traditional teaching method, and they do not know how to teach in

diversified classrooms, including students with hearing problems (Hattie et al., 1996). From this fact, it is clear that the state needs to recruit inclusive teachers in every community school to make teaching more effective (Wall, 2002). The government can also organize special education training periodically with necessary skills such as Braille and sign language. In the same context as above, participant S4 asserted, when I read in the resource class, I can understand hard with the help of sign language. The interaction is made easily in the resource class, but when I go to the integrated classroom, I am deprived of the opportunity. The non-disabled peers underestimate us saying Vahiro. We could understand if the regular teacher managed the sign language interpretation.

In this above assertion, the students are still a victim of labeling by conventional thought. Average students come from different backgrounds and have different mindsets due to the lack of a model of disability awareness; they exhibit dogmatic ideology and discriminatory thoughts (Susanti & Rudiwati, 2019). As above narratives, participant S2 said, I am facing the same challenges in the regular classroom. I cannot express all matters as per the teacher's speech in a regular class in Braille. The non-disabled peer also does not know how to support us. The integrated classroom seemed to be just an integration of disabled and non-disabled students without the necessary support.

From the above statement, it is clear that there are varieties of challenges that obstruct smooth adaptation. These challenges are constraints for psychosocial adjustment in the regular class. The traditional means of instruction cannot address the demand of children with disability. Skills such as Braille and sign language are essential for all types of students in regular school to create a collaborative environment in class (Hong et al., 2017). In such cases, the regular teacher needs to adopt differentiated instruction to support all types of children.

Lack of Expanded Core Curriculum

The expanded core curriculum is the knowledge and skill required for children with disability and the expertise and agility offered by the mainstream curriculum (Lieberman et al., 2014). The students are not provided additional knowledge and skills besides the existing curriculum. In this context, participant S3 emphasized as, children with disability are not hungering for the repertoire of theoretical knowledge, but instead, we need the necessary skill and expertise to run out of daily life. The general education teacher does not like to skip from depositing traditional theoretical knowledge because the conventional approach dominates overall learning strategies.

In this statement, the children with disability are not educated by using an expanded core curriculum. The meaning of theoretical knowledge is not much support and life carrier for children with a disability because students demand to learn how to have a settlement in society (Sapp & Hatlen, 2010). Basic skills and knowledge about life skills are essential for students with disability. So the regular teacher frequently focuses on delivering skill-based education in addition to the core curriculum.

Lack of Peer Support

The additional support offered by the non-disabled peer during reading refers to the peer support in a regular class (Tuttle & Carter, 2022). It is very much essential, especially for children with disability who cannot follow the instruction of the teacher. Regarding this matter, participant S2 asserted, We interact and share learning ways when I stay in the resource class. In resource class, we face common problems and solve them ourselves with the help of a support teacher. But I could not have such an opportunity in the regular class while taking the course.

In the above version, the students are experiencing an uneasy situation in a regular class without proper support from siblings. Generally, the non-disabled peers interact with regular students and share feelings with them in an accessible, frank manner. In such conditions, the student with a disability feels alone and deprived of classroom engagement in regular classes (Kef & Deković, 2004). In such a situation teacher must bridge between ordinary and students with additional needs. In the same context, another participant, S3, said, My bitter experience is that no friends support me during class. Sometimes I could not follow the teacher's instructions perfectly and felt confused due to my vision problem. At this moment, friends refuse to assist me due to the fear of being late for running class.

In this statement, the students with a disability seek support from their non-disabled peers for attractive interaction in class, but non-disabled peer feels not like doing that due to the limited time (Ely, 2014). In such cases, the teacher needs to provide an opportunity for students with disability to hold the class. The non-disabled students need to be aware of collaboration with students with disability (Celeste & Grum, 2010). The teacher needs to consider the multicultural class as beautiful to achieve the organization's goal.

Psychological Attachment

The emotional attachment to non-disabled peers in the regular class correlates with the psychological environment. This is the spiritual connection with classmates and in-depth interaction with friends (Cook et al., 2000). The psychological attachment towards the classroom promotes the frequency of engagement in the learning process (Murray & Greenberg, 2006). In this context, participant S2 asserted, Sometimes I feel alone when friends are attending sports meetings because I cannot participate effectively with my sighted friends. Although I like to play with them and feel backwards in the direction of the teacher for content areas because my friends follow the instruction easily, I cannot.

In this quotation, the children with disability are feeling humiliated by their hearts. Even though the sighted peer does not discriminate against children with disability, they feel uneasy compared to their non-disabled peers (Daniel, 1997). The respective teachers need to create a non-discriminatory environment so that children with a disability can feel identical to their typical peers (Skiba et al., 2006). The schools need to organize disable friendly sports, and teachers' demonstrations need to be related to tactile figures (Sherpa &

Baraily, 2021). For the psychological support of students with disability, disabled extracurricular social activities need to be introduced. Appreciating the above quotation, participant S4 emphasized as, I like to play with a friend but cannot participate with total effort because of my pitfalls. Participation in extracurricular activities keeps socio-emotional relations with colleagues. Due to my low performance in sports, the team may be disqualified. As a result, the will should be killed to participate in sports competitions. Quiz contests, speech contests and music competitions are frequently organized within the school.

In this assertion, extracurricular activity is essential for the overall development of a child. Active participation in extracurricular activities keeps the mind fresh and maintains social harmony within the class (Murray & Greenberg, 2006). The knowledge of solidarity and moral education is achieved through interaction with friends. Administrative supports are also essential for successful integration into extracurricular activity around the development of children with disability (Sijuola, 2022). Cognitive development is insufficient for student development for their career-seeking path.

Lack of Orientation about Changing Curriculum

The change of curriculum and subject matter to address the societal need of a person is considered to be the change in curriculum. The amendment in subject matter updates the needs of learners and society according to changes in time (Van Deventer & Steyn, 2022). The rigidity of the curriculum cannot support the reformation of society and nation development. The present children are the nation builder of future days. So, the curriculum needs to be amended according to societal demand and the impact of globalization (Wehmeyer et al., 2001). Before introducing a new curriculum in school the dissemination of the curriculum need to be carried out in the school district (McBeath, 1997). In this context participant S1 said, the course is frequently changing and contents are modified in every subject. The same teacher is teaching us traditional techniques. We are not feeling the advanced method of teaching in the changed curriculum. Sometimes it takes to come new books in this school and the teacher is teaching the same old book. We get the information about the change of curriculum but the teacher says no new book is coming till now.

In the above relation, the courses are changed from time to time but the teacher and students are not oriented about the new contents. The arrival of the new curriculum is delayed due to the less accountability of school administration towards the learning of students (Starmer et al., 2014). The teacher depends on the changed book but it is not available due to the lack of coordination with the relevant department. It seems that some of the head teachers are not intending to approach the new curriculum and textbook due to a lack of awareness (Van Deventer & Steyn, 2022). On the other side, the monitoring mechanism is very weak in our context after the introduction of the new curriculum. So the school administrations need to be very sensitive to manage the curriculum and teaching material as soon as possible. The school also focuses on conducting a course dissemination program for teachers.

Another participant said. The regular education curriculum has been changing every year with new content and materials. But the resources are not added to the previous one. In the English Braille book contraction is added more. Most of the visually impaired students and regular teachers cannot understand the contraction. So we feel English subject very hard to read. The teacher and students are not oriented about the changed context of the curriculum before the sessions begin.

Concerning to above argument, the general class curriculum is frequently changing after a certain period. The teaching material is regularly changed according to societal needs (Van Deventer & Steyn, 2022). But the pedagogical transformation has not been done in the teaching-learning process. The activity in the learning process is remaining the same as in previous days. In the case of children with disability, the learning material is not modified (Wehmeyer et al., 2001). The Braille books for children with visual impairment are becoming complicated with a lot of contraction which is difficult to deliver content for teachers and hard to understand for average-minded students (Pacheco, 2016). In this context, the teaching material needs to be made simpler with understandable content. The frequent use of contraction is discouraged in every teaching material like references and textbooks. The contraction dictionary is made accessible to all learners and teachers for effective teaching-learning activities (Vik & Lassen, 2010). The optimum use of teaching material is also introduced in every class for perceptual understanding. In the same context as above another participant said, I need to spend most of the study hours in the regular class with non-disabled peers. Only for a certain amount of time, we are allowed to go to resource class for compensatory skills like Braille and sign language. In the curriculum amendment, the skills and knowledge are not amended accordingly. Instead of shifting to resource class, it is better to teach basic skills in the regular class in the presence of a special teacher.

Concerning to above, the students are encouraged to know acquiring tasks in the resource class for a certain period. Since knowledge is constructed through social interaction with the mutual sharing of ideas (Juvova et al., 2015). So, collaborative environments with mutual understanding need to be created in regular classes for the acquisition of knowledge. The general and special teachers are oriented with new knowledge and skills for imparting sound education (Agran et al., 2002).

CONCLUSIONS

Children with disability generally face emotional challenges due to frequent adjustment trouble in academic success (Peek & Stough, 2010). The children with disability have expressed their destructive feeling in transportation, calming down, and difficulty following the teacher's directions in the classroom, active participation in extracurricular activity and effective engagement in a learning environment with non-disabled friends. Students with hidden disabilities may demonstrate undesirable behavior for various reasons that obstruct learning (Bear et al., 2020). Students with a disability may feel anxiety, frustration, and sadness, hopeless due to their difficulties.

Frustration may arise due to the lack of administrative support in the evaluation process. The students with visual impairment can not reflect their potentiality in writing with the provision of the writer. Lack of introduction to Braille in the assessment process may cause psychological pain for intelligent students. The physical, administrative, and attitudinal limitations have appeared to be the significant challenges for adjustment in mainstreaming .mainly, students with disability approaches to disrupt the classroom with their behavior issues (Dickson, 2011). Because some students with disability are not cognitively developed as typical peers, they cannot compete with them. In other words, traditional teaching methods still dominate our teaching-learning environment. In the contemporary situation, it isn't easy to address the need of every student in the regular class (Kristensen et al., 2003). Due to the lack of adequate training for inclusive education for regular teachers, teaching students with special needs is more challenging. The teacher who teaches in the regular class needs to use differentiated instruction. Students with disabilities are deprived of the right to education if treated in the integrated classroom without additional support (Adegboyega, 2019).

ADVANCED RESEARCH

In the regular classroom, children with a disability may face academic, social, emotional, and psychological problems. To overcome such challenges, the parents, teachers and administrators need to be equally responsible within and outside of school.

REFERENCES

- Adegboyega, L. O. (2019). Challenges and adjustment needs of students with special needs in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. *IFE Psychologia: An International Journal*, 27(1), 61-74.
- Agesa, L. (2014). Challenges faced by learners with visual impairments in inclusive settings in Trans-Nzoia County. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(29), 185-192.
- Agran, M., Alper, S., & Wehmeyer, M. (2002). Access to the general curriculum for students with significant disabilities: What it means to teachers. *Education and Training in Mental Retardation and Developmental Disabilities*, 123-133.
- Al-Makahleh, A. A. A. (2011). The Effect of Direct Instruction Strategy on Math Achievement of Primary 4th and 5th Grade Students with Learning Difficulties. *International Education Studies*, 4(4), 199-205.
- Baraga, E., & Van Kampen, M. (1983). Watson, c., Czekala, J., & Kuhne, A. Defining post-traumatic stress disorder: Are the DSM-all criteria necessary and sufficient? *Unpublished Manuscript That Provides Preliminary Data Concerning DSM-III PTSD Criteria for an in-Patient Substance Abusing Population. Veterans Administration Medical Center, St. Cloud, MN.*
- Barnes, C., & Mercer, G. (2005). Disability, work, and welfare: Challenging the social exclusion of disabled people. *Work, Employment and Society*, 19(3), 527-545.
- Bear, A., Drew, C., Zuckerman, K. E., & Phelps, R. A. (2020). Understanding

- barriers to access and utilization of developmental disability services facilitates the transition. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*, 41(9), 680–689.
- Bickford, J. O., & Falco, R. A. (2012). Technology for early braille literacy: Comparison of traditional braille instruction and instruction with an electronic notetaker. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 106(10), 679–693.
- Bos, C. S., Coleman, M., & Vaughn, S. (2002). Reading and students with E/BD: What do we know and recommend? *Interventions for Children with or at Risk for Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*, 87–103.
- Celeste, M., & Grum, D. K. (2010). Social integration of children with visual impairment: A developmental model. *İlköğretim Online*, 9(1), 11–22.
- Chomba, M. J., Mukuria, S. G., Kariuki, P. W., Tumuti, S., & Bunyasi, B. A. (2014). Education for students with intellectual disabilities in Kenya: Challenges and prospects. *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 34(4).
- Cook, B. G., Tankersley, M., Cook, L., & Landrum, T. J. (2000). Teachers' attitudes toward their included students with disabilities. *Exceptional Children*, 67(1), 115–135.
- Cox, P. R., & Dykes, M. K. (2001). Effective Classroom Adaptations for Students with Visual Impairments. *TEACHING Exceptional Children*, 33(6), 68–74. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004005990103300609>
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Steps in conducting a scholarly mixed methods study*.
- Daniel, P. T. K. (1997). Educating students with disabilities in the least restrictive environment: A slippery slope for educators. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 35(5), 397–410.
- Dekker, R. (1993). Visually impaired children and haptic intelligence test scores: Intelligence Test for Visually Impaired Children (ITVIC). *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 35(6), 478–489.
- Dickson, E. (2011). Reasonable adjustment and the assessment of students with disabilities: Australian legal issues and trends. *Sustainable Education, Schools, Families and Communities-Education Law and Policy Perspectives: Proceedings of the 2011 Australia and New Zealand Education Law Association (ANZELA) Conference*, 22–31.
- DiGennaro Reed, F. D., McIntyre, L. L., Dusek, J., & Quintero, N. (2011). Preliminary assessment of friendship, problem behaviour, and social adjustment in children with disabilities in an inclusive education setting. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 23(6), 477–489.
- Ely, M. S. (2014). Effective strategies for preschool peer group entry: considered applications for children with visual impairments. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 108(4), 287–297.
- Forlin, C. (1995). Educators' beliefs about inclusive practices in Western Australia. *British Journal of Special Education*, 22(4), 179–185.
- Hattie, J., Biggs, J., & Purdie, N. (1996). Effects of learning skills interventions on student learning: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 66(2), 99–136.
- Hong, S., Rosenblum, L. P., & Campbell, A. F. (2017). Implementation of

- Unified English Braille by teachers of students with visual impairments in the United States. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 111(6), 543–556.
- Ivancevich, J. M., & Gilbert, J. A. (2000). Diversity management: Time for a new approach. *Public Personnel Management*, 29(1), 75–92.
- Jindal-Snape, D. (2004). Generalization and maintenance of social skills of children with visual impairments: Self-evaluation and the role of feedback. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 98(8), 470–483.
- Juvova, A., Chudy, S., Neumeister, P., Plischke, J., & Kvintova, J. (2015). Reflection of constructivist theories in current educational practice. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 3(5), 345–349.
- Kef, S., & Deković, M. (2004). The role of parental and peer support in adolescents well-being: a comparison of adolescents with and without a visual impairment. *Journal of Adolescence*, 27(4), 453–466.
- Kendall, L. (2018). Supporting students with disabilities within a UK university: Lecturer perspectives. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 55(6), 694–703.
- Kristensen, K., Omagor-Loican, M., & Onen, N. (2003). The inclusion of learners with barriers to learning and development into ordinary school settings: a challenge for Uganda. *British Journal of Special Education*, 30(4), 194–201.
- Kumar, A., Chaturvedi, R. K., & Mishra, S. (n.d.). *Advocate of Equal Opportunity in Education: Normalization Principle*.
- Kurth, J. A., & Keegan, L. (2014). Development and use of curricular adaptations for students receiving special education services. *The Journal of Special Education*, 48(3), 191–203.
- Leach, D., & Duffy, M. Lou. (2009). Supporting students with autism spectrum disorders in inclusive settings. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 45(1), 31–37.
- Liasidou, A. (2012). Inclusive education and critical pedagogy at the Intersections of disability, race, gender and class. *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies*, 10, 168–184. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ970851>
- Lieberman, L. J., Haegele, J. A., Columba, L., & Conroy, P. (2014). How students with visual impairments can learn components of the expanded core curriculum through physical education. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 108(3), 239–248.
- Lohmeier, K. L. (2005). Implementing the expanded core curriculum in specialized schools for the blind. *RE: View*, 37(3), 126.
- Maltz, C. (1962). *A Measure of the Significance of Pattern Features for Use as an Aid in the Design of Recognition Systems*. CALIFORNIA UNIV LOS ANGELES.
- McBeath, C. (1997). Curriculum dissemination: a problematic issue in educational change. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Vocational Education Research*, 5(2), 37–55.
- Mitchell, R., Boyle, B., Parker, V., Giles, M., Chiang, V., & Joyce, P. (2015). Managing inclusiveness and diversity in teams: How leader inclusiveness affects performance through status and team identity. *Human Resource Management*, 54(2), 217–239.
- Mukhopadhyay, S., Nenty, H. J., & Abosi, O. (2012). Inclusive education for learners with disabilities in Botswana primary schools. *Sage Open*, 2(2),

2158244012451584.

- Murray, C., & Greenberg, M. T. (2006). Examining the importance of social relationships and social contexts in the lives of children with high-incidence disabilities. *The Journal of Special Education, 39*(4), 220–233.
- Neeraja, P., & Anuradha, K. (2014). Adjustment problems faced by children with learning disabilities impact special education. *Indian Journal of Scientific Research, 5*(1), 77–81.
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education, 8*(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-019-0509-2>
- Pacheco, E. (2016). *Vision impairment and the transition to university education: The role of ICTs*.
- Peek, L., & Stough, L. M. (2010). Children with disabilities in the context of disaster: A social vulnerability perspective. *Child Development, 81*(4), 1260–1270.
- Preeti, T., & Kiran, U. V. (2012). Infrastructural Facilities for Differently Abled Students-A Comparative Study of Government and Non-Government Institutions. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences, 1*(3), 21–25.
- Pugach, M. C. (2005). Research on preparing general education teachers to work with students with disabilities. *Studying Teacher Education: The Report of the AERA Panel on Research and Teacher Education, 549–590*.
- Ruhl, K. L., & Suritsky, S. (1995). The pause procedure and/or an outline: Effect on immediate free recall and lecture notes taken by college students with learning disabilities. *Learning Disability Quarterly, 18*(1), 2–11.
- Sapp, W., & Hatlen, P. (2010). The expanded core curriculum: Where we have been, where we are going, and how we can get there. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness, 104*(6), 338–348.
- Sherpa, D., & Baraily, K. (2021). Exploration of Teachers' Role in Resource Class: A Case from an Integrated School. *AMC Journal, 2*(1), 41–55.
- Sijuola, R. (2022). Inclusive education for people living with disabilities in Nigeria. *Rural Environment, Education, Personality, 15*, 148–153.
- Skiba, R. J., Poloni-Staudinger, L., Gallini, S., Simmons, A. B., & Feggins-Azziz, R. (2006). Disparate access: The disproportionality of African American students with disabilities across educational environments. *Exceptional Children, 72*(4), 411–424.
- Soodak, L. C., & McCarthy, M. R. (2013). Classroom management in inclusive settings. In *Handbook of classroom management* (pp. 471–500). Routledge.
- Starmer, A. J., O'Toole, J. K., Rosenbluth, G., Calaman, S., Balmer, D., West, D. C., Bale Jr, J. F., Clifton, E. Y., Noble, E. L., & Lisa, L. T. (2014). Development, implementation, and dissemination of the I-PASS handoff curriculum: a multisite educational intervention to improve patient handoffs. *Academic Medicine, 89*(6), 876–884.
- Sucuoglu, B., Akalin, S., & Sazak-Pinar, E. (2010). The effects of classroom management on the behaviours of students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms in Turkey. *Journal of the International Association of Special Education, 11*(1), 64–74.

- Susanti, D. J., & Rudiyati, S. (2019). Learn writing and reading braille for an elementary student with visual impairment: a systematic review. *International Conference on Special and Inclusive Education (ICSIE 2018)*, 176–180.
- Tuttle, M., & Carter, E. W. (2022). Examining peer support arrangements for students with visual impairment. *British Journal of Visual Impairment*, 40(2), 222–239.
- Vakil, S., Welton, E., O'Connor, B., & Kline, L. S. (2009). Inclusion means everyone! The role of the early childhood educator when including young children with autism in the classroom. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 36(4), 321–326.
- Van Deventer, A., & Steyn, R. (2022). Teachers' attitudes towards the amendments in the Design curriculum: a critical overview of the approach and findings of the study. *Design and Technology Education: An International Journal*, 27(2), 53–69.
- Van Lankveld, T., Schoonenboom, J., Volman, M., Croiset, G., & Beishuizen, J. (2017). Developing a teacher identity in the university context: A systematic review of the literature. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 36(2), 325–342.
- Vaughn, S., Levy, S., Coleman, M., & Bos, C. S. (2002). Reading instruction for students with LD and EBD: A synthesis of observational studies. *The Journal of Special Education*, 36(1), 2–13.
- Wall, R. (2002). Teachers' exposure to people with visual impairments and the effect on attitudes toward inclusion. *RE: View*, 34(3), 111.
- Wang, Y. (2016). *Imagining inclusive schooling: an ethnographic inquiry into disabled children's learning and participation in regular schools in Shanghai*. The University of Edinburgh.
- Wehmeyer, M. L., Lattin, D., & Agran, M. (2001). Achieving access to the general curriculum for students with mental retardation: A curriculum decision-making model. *Education and Training in Mental Retardation and Developmental Disabilities*, 327–342.
- Wilhelmsen, T., & Sørensen, M. (2017). Inclusion of children with disabilities in physical education: A systematic review of literature from 2009 to 2015. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 34(3), 311–337.
- Wilson, C. L., & Sindelar, P. T. (1991). Direct instruction in math word problems: Students with learning disabilities. *Exceptional Children*, 57(6), 512–519.
- Yan, X., Chen, L., & Yan, H. (2019). Socio-economic status, visual impairment and the mediating role of lifestyles in developed rural areas of China. *PLoS One*, 14(4), e0215329.
- Zaunda, H., Holm, R., Itimu-Phiri, A., Malota, M., & White, S. (2018). A qualitative assessment of disability-friendly water and sanitation facilities in primary schools, Rumphu, Malawi. *Development Southern Africa*, 35(6),